

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to GM infestation in the field. Karnataka, India, 1990-92 WS.

Av percentage of tillers as shoots	Lines
0-5	IET9689, IET10260, IET10770, IET11162, IET10747, IET10775, IET12489, IET10765, IET10247, IET10867, IET10312, IET7428, IET9552, IET10418, IET11396, IET10765, Shakti, Phalguna, KKP6, KKP2
5-10	IET6461, IET11089, IET11122, IET11465, IET7830, IET7303, IET10751, IET10864, IET10668, IET3039, IET7956, MO 4, Cul 170, Cul 168, KMS83-1, GMR17
10-20	IET10333, IET11452, IET10735, IET10318, CTH1, MO 5, MO 6, MO 7, Cul 204, Cul 126, Cul 170, Cul 93, Cul 153-1, Cul 22332-2, Cul 200, Annapurna, Bharathi
20 or more	IET10748, Jaya (check)

Rice cultures resistant to rice gall midge (GM) biotypes 1 and 4 under artificial infestation in greenhouse

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At least four distinct GM biotypes exist in India. We have been rearing biotypes 1 and 4 (both prevalent in AP) under strict greenhouse isolation conditions. Biotype 1 (the original Hyderabad population) has been maintained on TN1 at DRR since 1976. Biotype 4 was built up from the endemic population of Srikakulam district, AP, and is maintained on Phalguna rice, which is resistant to biotype 1 and susceptible to biotype 4.

We evaluated 1,295 elite breeding lines from DRR-coordinated national yield and observational nurseries against the two biotypes. The standard screening

Advanced breeding lines of rice showing resistance to GM biotypes 1 and 4 in greenhouse, DDR, Hyderabad, AP, India, 1988-90.

Line	Designation	Cross	Source of resistance against	
			Biotype 1	Biotypes 1 and 4
IET10743 IET10742 IET11377	CR309 selections	Orumundakan/ CRM6-106		Orumundakan
IET11375	CR308-38	Orumundakan/ Damodar		Orumundakan
-	CR308-408	Orumundakan/ Damodar		Orumundakan
-	CR311-34	Orumundakan/ Dasal		Orumundakan
-	CR311-134	Orumundakan/ Dasal		Orumundakan
-	CRM24	Orumundakan mutant		Orumundakan
IET9709 IET9710 IET9711 IET9853 IET9854 IET10300 IET10746 IET10831 IET10849 IET11104	RP2068 selections	Swarnadhan/ Velluthacheera		Velluthacheera
-	R296 selections	CR157-392/ OR57-21		Ptb10
-	CR157-912	Vijaya/Ptb10		Ptb10
-	RP1528-1237-39	CR97-1550/ARC7328		Ptb21
IET11483	RTN14-1-1-1	IR36/CR57-MR1523		Ptb21
IET11384	RTN121-1-1-1-1	CR57-MR1523/IR36// RTN68		Ptb21
IET11385	RTN332-4-2-1	CR57-40/RTN711		Ptb21
IET11452	RTN29-1-1	CR57-MR1523/IR36		Ptb21
-	WGL 47805	BPT3301/CR57-MR1523		Ptb21
IET10744	CR386-23-5-4	ARC6650/CR94-721-3		Ptb18 Ptb21
IET10412	CR407-6-1	CR94/Ratna		Ptb21
IET12348	CR404-14-1	CR94-1512-6/Usa 2-21		Ptb21
-	RP2629-44-33-21	IET8682/IR60		Ptb21
IET10371	Pusa 510	IR36/Pusa 167		Ptb21
IET11164	R281-12	Poorva/IR8608-298		Ptb21
IET10885	TNAU842805	TNAU9426-6/IR50		Ptb21
IET12364	MTU6203	MTU4570/IR50		Ptb21
IET10247	OR633-7	Jajati/Ob677	Ob677	
IET11508	RP2543 selections	Rasi/RP1579-39	Siam 29	
IET11517 IET12873	RP2547-130-272	ARC5723/ARC6650// RP1579-38	Siam 29	
-	RP2547-100-255	RP1579-38	Siam 29	
-	RP2547-111-259	RP1579-38	Siam 29	
IET10451	OR487-30-3	T90/IR8/RPW6-13// Siam 29	Siam 29	
-	OR447-20-8	IR8/Siam 29// Parijat///Rasi	Siam 29	
IET11514	RP1959-56- 88-426-30-52	Swarnadhan/Phalguna	Siam 29	
-	RP2541-8642-357	Swarnadhan/RP1579-36	Siam 29	

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Table continued.

Designation	Cross	Source of resistance against	
		Biotype 1	Biotypes 1 and 4
IET12523 IET12524 IET12525	RP2231 selections Phalguna/ Velluthacheera	Siam 29	Velluthacheera
IET10762 IET11470 -	RP2432-68-11-9 RP1607-1240-42 RP2434-45-3-2	IR36/IET7916 Phalguna/MR1523 IR50/IET7918	Siam 29 Ptb18, Ptb21 Siam 29 Ptb18, Ptb21 Siam 29 Ptb18, Ptb21
IET10891 IET12871	RP2235-179-16-10 WGL 46753	Phalguna/IR50 Surekha/WGL 16145	Siam 29 Ptb18, Ptb21 Siam 29, -
IET10850 IET10851 IET10517 IET10314 IET10312 IET10313	R321 selections CR401-6-1 WR6-120-10 CR380 selections CR41/CO 39	Samridhi/IR36 Vijaya/CR904 IR62/Parmel CRII/Ratna	Eswarakora Ptb18, Ptb21 ? ? ?
IET10407 IET12349 -	TNAU801790 CR30-20-1 RR217-1	CR41/CO 39 IR8/Sigadis IR17491-5-4-3/ IR2415-90-4-3// IR9129-209-2-2	? ? ?

test was used under greenhouse conditions from 1988 to 1990, and replicated four times. Sixty cultures were found resistant to both biotypes (see table). None of the biotype 4-resistant cultures were susceptible to biotype 1, but all of the cultures susceptible to biotype 1 were also susceptible to biotype 4.

Resistance to both biotypes was contributed mainly to the lines by Orumundakan, Velluthacheera, Ptb10, Ptb21, and combinations of two or more donors. Nine cultures exhibiting resistance were derivatives of Siam 29, which is, like its derivative Phalguna, resistant to biotype 1 but susceptible to biotype 4. The other parents involved in cross combinations with Siam 29 and its derivatives probably contributed or modified the resistance reaction in these cultures.

Further studies on reactions of parents involved in these crosses might identify additional gene sources for resistance. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Brown planthopper (BPH)- resistant cultivars from Madhya Pradesh Rice Research Institute (MPRRI) germplasm

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Host plant resistance is an important component of pest management programs to control *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål. To stay ahead of the emergence of new insect biotypes, improved resistant cultivars with more genetic diversity must be developed.

We evaluated 900 MPRRI rice cultivars during 1990-92 to locate better sources of BPH resistance. We infested 9- to 10-d-old test seedlings and checks TN1 and Ptb33 with 1st- and 2d-instar BPH nymphs. Damage to seedlings was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0-9) scale. Cultivars scoring less than three were retested three to six times. Sixty-nine cultivars were

BPH-resistant cultivars from MPRRI germplasm.

Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin	Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin
Kakadi	K:2531	1.9	Bastar	Kakadiha	K:1832	1.6	Raipur
Chhoti Kanhai	C:758	2.9	Bastar	Kali Kamod	K:224	2.4	Raipur
Kanhaiya	K:2167	2.9	Bastar	Kanthgulas	K:711 III	2.5	Raipur
Dodki	D:1015	1.2	Bastar	Bhatha Dhouri	B:2876	1.1	Raipur
Farsa Phool	F:16	0.1	Bastar	Dhumki	D:1114	1.5	Raipur
Bhata-Gada-Khuta	B:803 II	2.3	Bastar	Dokalam	D:279	1.1	Raipur
Gada Khota	G:978	1.7	Bastar	Kankadiya	K:1699	2.9	Raigarh
Hinga	H:435	0.7	Bastar	Dokalam	D:455 III	2.0	Raipur
Jalki	J:287III	1.3	Bastar	Hathi Panjada	H:218	0.2	Raipur
Kabari	K:2312	2.8	Bastar	Hasa	H:56	2.4	Raipur
Kabari	K:2388	2.5	Bastar	Jagnath	J:55 II	2.1	Raipur
Kanhaiya	K:2413	2.3	Bastar	Prasad			
Kappe	K:1592	2.3	Bastar	Jaybay Rang	J:432	0.0	Raipur
Bas Bhira	B:2655	2.6	Bastar	Karhani	K:556 II	1.7	Raipur
Barangi	B:1862	1.3	Bastar	Karhani	K:1173	1.7	Raipur
Basangi	B:2682	0.6	Bastar	Khatia Pati	K:60	1.9	Raipur
Bhainspath	B:61 I	2.0	Bastar	Kalam	K:1167 I	2.7	Sarguja
Kalamdani	K:2478	1.8	Raigarh	Kalamdani	K:1163	2.6	Sarguja
Kankadiya	K:430	1.6	Raigarh	Dhouri	D:8011	3.0	Sarguja
Kandradiya	K:446 II	1.5	Raigarh	Karhani	K:1911	2.6	Sarguja
Dokalam	D:455 II	1.5	Raipur	Kanai	K:1885	2.4	Bilaspur
Dhouri	D:1043	0.7	Raigarh	Khondharo			
Dhouri	D:1163	2.0	Raigarh	Kanak	K:1741	2.4	Bilaspur
Dhouri	D:1167	2.0	Raigarh	Kankadiya	K:652	2.4	Bilaspur
Bhatha Dhouri	B:1651	1.6	Raigarh	Kapursar	K:1798	2.7	Bilaspur
Gang Puriha	G:809	2.0	Raigarh	Karapari	K:164	2.3	Bilaspur
Dahi Barhi	D:1771	2.0	Raigarh	Dhori Sulti	D:1070	1.9	Bilaspur
				Ganga Prasad	G:760	3.0	Bilaspur

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